

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING REPLACES TRADITIONAL TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN MANAGEMENT INSTITUTE

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ABSTRACT

Traditional teaching methodology is based mainly on knowledge/skills transfer, but this does not address individual growth. Experiential learning is a powerful way to address individual growth and potential, which is neglected approach to teaching but developing people of all ages. It is adaptable for individual style, preferences, strengths, direction, etc. This paper focuses on identifying the concept of experiential learning, and how experiential learning helps in improving the understanding and practical implementation of subject.

KEY WORD: *Experiential Learning, Teacher centered method, reflective learning, whole self involvement*

INTRODUCTION

The traditional teacher-centred atmosphere of the college classroom has been criticized for not fostering a student's ability to think. The learner's role is submissive, where he or she is only a participant in the learning process. This scenario is an example of a typical tradition teaching methodology. Now, imagine a classroom where the teacher involves the student in the entire learning process, from the decision of what will be learned to the evaluation of what was learned—from the beginning to the end. This scenario is an example of experiential learning. An experiential learning approach to teaching fosters a deep approach to learning, where students are required to think critically. The way a college instructor teaches influences how his or her students learn. Experiential learning, as defined by

Luckmann 1996, is “a process through which a learner constructs knowledge, skill, and value from direct experience”.

Savitribai Phule Pune University is continuously revising the syllabus in every two to three years; recently university has revised the syllabus which will be applicable with effect from academic year 2016-17 onwards. The university also tries to focus new teaching methodology due to dynamic business environment after consulting the concern of industry. University introduced continuous assessment system in semester system (also known as internal assessment/comprehensive assessment) is spread through the duration of course and is done by the teacher teaching the course. Concurrent evaluation components should be designed in such a way that the faculty can *monitor the student learning & development and intervene wherever required*. In this assessment of student capabilities can be done across Knowledge, Skills & Attitude (KSA) dimensions based on variety of assessment tools. There are few Suggested components for Concurrent Evaluation (CE) which is focused on experiential learning such as Case Study / Caselet / Situation Analysis, Field Visit / Study Tour, Small Group Project & Internal Viva-Voce, Role Play / Story Telling, Industry Analysis or Model Development / Simulation Exercises.

DEFINITION

In the words of Lewis and Williams (1994, p.5) “In its simplest form, experiential learning means learning from experience or learning by doing. Experiential education first immerses learners in an experience and then encourages reflection about the experience to develop new skills, new attitudes, or new ways of thinking.”

In Kolb’s Experiential Learning Cycle, the learner utilizes two strategies for grasping experiences—Concrete Experience (CE) and Abstract Conceptualization (AC), and the learner utilizes two strategies for transforming experiences—Reflective Observation (RO) and Active Experimentation (AE)

OBJECTIVE

1. To understand the importance of experiential learning practice.
2. To analyze the impact of experiential learning practice on students understanding of the topic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Rogers (1969), states in his book that experiential learning encourages personal input, initiative, and self-direction in the learning process. Activities begin with accessing the specific past experiences of students, and then building on these experiences to construct a framework for learning unique to the requirements and learning style of each student. Koenderman (2000) provides an experiential model based on these elements, a series of phases that outline the sequencing of classroom activities from the introduction of a topic or theme to the conclusion. In the *exposure phase* a topic is introduced, and students are given the opportunity to reflect on their own experiences in this area and to relate the topic to their personal leaning goals; in the *participation phase* the students become personally involved as they participate in an activity, either in the classroom or outside, intended to build on or enhance their previous experience; in the *internalization phase* a debriefing exercise is initiated by the teacher, and the students have the opportunity to reflect on their participation in the activity and discuss potential effects on their future behavior or attitudes; and finally, in the *dissemination or transfer phase* the students apply and present their learning, linking it with the world outside the classroom. Fatemeh Mollaei, Hamidreza Rahnama (2012), elaborated on historical background of how experiential education has emerged, and how it has been adopted to the field of language education. It focuses on identifying the concept of experiential learning, an experiential learning cycle, its principles and criteria, weaknesses and strengths. Researcher found experiential learning is participative, interactive, and applied. Through experience, learners are able to construct firsthand sense of understanding of the events going on around them. All previous research related to experiential

learning proves that the division of the learning process into experiential phases helps sequence the learning activities toward the achievement of the desired learning outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was confined to study the impact of experiential learning on the students understanding of the subject. The students understanding can be evaluated using two parameters i.e. reflective experience and whole self involvement in lecture. The student involvement in a reflective experience enables him/ her to relate current learning to past, present and future, even if these relationships are felt rather than thought and whole self involvement means involvement of body, thoughts, feelings and actions, not just of the mind; in other words, the student is engaged as a whole person.

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The importance of experiential learning was studied from the literature review of various journals. Two samples of 60 students from management institute of Savitribai Phule Pune University is taken out of which first sample of 60 students attended traditional learning methodology and second sample of 60 students attended experiential learning methodology and the evaluation of their understanding in both methods of learning is taken. The data for the study was gathered through self administered feedback form. The first part of the questionnaire comprised of question about demographic profile of the student. And the second part of the questionnaire comprised of questions about the understanding of topic taught which is filled by the students.

HYPOTHESES

H₁₀: There is no significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to improvement in reflective experience.

H1_A: There is significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to improvement in reflective experience.

H2_O: There is no significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to student’s involvement in whole self.

H2_A: There is significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to student’s involvement in whole self.

DISCUSSION AND FINDING

Analysis as conducted by using the statistical analysis tool SPSS version 19.0 (Two sample T test) in order to identify difference between experiential and traditional learning methodology with respect to improvement in reflective experience and student’s involvement in whole self.

Analysis of data is made keeping the objective of the study in mind. The demographic profile of the respondent is as follows:

Table 1: Demographic profile of the Respondent

Factors	Description	No. of Respondent
Gender	Male	89
	Female	31
Graduation Qualification	B. Com / B.B.A	45
	B. Sc /B.C.A	19
	B.A	25
	B. E	5
	Others	6
Percentage obtained in Graduation	Above 60%	66
	50 % - 60 %	44

The sample was taken carefully from all education background and IQ levels. Experiential teaching methodologies which can be used by instructor are as follows:

1. personal journals, diaries
2. portfolios
3. role plays, drama activities
4. games and simulations
5. personal stories and case studies
6. visualizations and imaginative activities
7. models, analogies and theory construction
8. empathy-taking activities
9. story-telling, sharing with others
10. discussions and reflection in cooperative groups

Researcher has taken two independent samples and evaluated their level of understanding after the session; students were analyzed on their reflective experience and whole self involvement. Researcher used independent two sample t test to check if there is a significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology.

Table 2: Experiential Learning Methodology Vs Traditional Teaching Methodology in gaining reflective experience

VAR00002	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std. Error Mean
VAR00001 Traditional Teaching	60	3.1333	0.63424	0.08188
Experiential Teaching	60	3.5500	0.59447	0.07675

With $df=29$, table value of T test is 2.000, The calculated t-value (2.525) is greater than the table value (2.000) at an alpha level of .05. Therefore, we reject null hypothesis and found that there is significant difference between experiential

learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to improvement in reflective experience.

Table 3: Experiential Learning Methodology Vs Traditional Teaching Methodology in student’s whole self-involvement

VAR00002	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std. Error Mean
VAR00001 Traditional Teaching	60	3.3000	0.64572	0.08336
Experiential Teaching	60	3.6000	0.58802	0.07591

	F	Sig	T Test for equality of Means	
			t	Sig (2 - Tailed)
VAR00001 Equal variance assumed	0.163	0.687	-2.661	0.009
Equal variance not assumed			-2.661	0.009

	F	Sig	T Test for equality of Means	
			t	Sig (2 - Tailed)
VAR00001 Equal variance assumed	0.058	0.810	-2.525	0.013
Equal variance not assumed			-2.525	0.013

With df=29, table value of T test is 2.000, The calculated t-value (2.661) is greater than the table value (2.000) at an alpha level of .05. Therefore, we reject null hypothesis and found that there is significant difference between experiential learning methodology and traditional teaching methodology with respect to student’s whole self-involvement.

The results of this research suggest the potential benefit of experiential learning methodology. The goal of experience-based learning engages students personally

and instructor also establishes a sense of trust, respect, openness, and concern for the well-being of the students.

CONCLUSION

Experiential learning is participative, interactive, and applied. It allows contact with the environment, and exposure to processes that are highly variable and uncertain. It involves the whole-person; learning takes place on the affective and behavioral dimensions as well as on the cognitive dimension. The experience needs to be structured to some degree; relevant learning objectives need to be specified and the conduct of the experience needs to be monitored. Students need to evaluate the experience in light of theory and in light of their own feelings. Experiential Learning Theory outlines the manner in which learner's gains knowledge and understanding through experiences. Though some may debate which steps are present in experiential learning, there is no debate about the worth of experience in learning. It suggests that the learner must occupy the centre stages of classroom activity and not the teacher. That the approaches which engage students in interdisciplinary exploration, collaborative activity and field based opportunities for experiential learning, reflection and self examination are used more and more by the teachers.

REFERENCES

- Rogers, C. (1969), Freedom to Learn. Columbus, OH: Charles E. Merrill.*
- Koenderman, M. (2000), Monitor training manual. Unpublished document. Sherbrooke, QC: English Language Summer School, Universite de Sherbrooke.*
- Fatemeh Mollaei, Hamidreza Rahnama (2012), Experiential Education Contributing to Language Learning, International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Vol. 2 No. 21; November 2012*